

REFERENCE OF LEXEMAS WITH THE GENERAL SYMPTOMS OF
"COURAGE" IN UZBEKI IN ETYMOLOGICAL DICTIONARIES

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ANNOTATION

In this article, the historical and etymological characteristics of the nouns with the common name "Courage", the fact that they have their own and borrowed layers, and that they are borrowed from Arabic, Persian, Mongolian, and Italian languages, are discussed. The Arabic layer of possessive nouns is richer compared to other layers, which is characterized by the fact that the Arabic layer has a large role in the formation of the Uzbek language.

Key words: courage, historical, etymological, lexeme, native layer, native layer, Arabic, Persian, Mongolian, Italian

Lexemes expressing concepts of courage have unique historical and etymological characteristics. The lexemes included in this system consist of microsystems related to their own and acquired layers. To the unities of one's: azimkor, azmkor, bardamlashmoq, bardamlik, baquvvatlik, bag'airat, bahodirlik, bahodirlarcha, bahodirona, bikir, bioquvvat, botirlanmoq, botirlarcha, botirlashmoq, botirlik, boshijoat, gurdalik, dadil, dadillanmoq, dadillashmoq, dadillik, dadilona, dovchi, dovyurak, yetuk, yetuklik, yovqurlik, jangovarlik, jasoratli, jasurlanmoq, jasurlik, jasurona, jonbozlik, juvonmardlik, jo'mard, jo'mardlik, zabardastlik, iktidorli, kuch, madadkor, mardonavor, pahlavonlarday, paxlavonlarcha, pahlavonlik, purqudrat, serg'ayrat, tetik, tetiklamoq, tetiklanmoq, tetiklashmoq, tetiklik, tinka, chog', yuksak, yuksaklik, yuksalish, yuksalmoq, qahramonlik, qirchillama, qirchillamoq, qodirlik, quvvatlamoq, darmon, darmonbaxsh, dildor, jangovar, zabardast, mard, navqiron, paxlavon, polvon, tavon, tavono, shud, qahramon, qahramonona ;

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v) Mongolian: bahodir, botir;

g) italian: virtuoz.

quvvatlanmoq, quvvatli, qudratli, qo'rqmas, g'ayratli, g'ayratchan, g'ujur belongs to such lexical units, most of them are characterized by creativity. [Mahmudov T. 2001:140]

Self-level units are divided into the following groups:

a) Arabic: azamat, azimat, azm, jabbor, jasorat, jasur, jur'at, iqtidor, madad, savlat, sobit, shavkat, shiddat, shiddatkor, shijoat, shijoatkor, qodir, quvva, quvvat, qudrat, g'alaba va b.;

b) Persian: bazo'r, bardam,

The Arabic layer of possessive nouns is richer compared to other layers, which is characterized by the fact that the Arabic layer has a large role in the formation of the Uzbek language. Therefore, among the lexemes, the name expressing the concepts of Courage is distinguished by the priority of the number of lexical units belonging to the Arabic language or based on Arabic. For example, the word courage borrowed from the Arabic language is explained as follows in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language.

COURAGE - mardlik, qo'rqmaslik; shijoat] Qahramonlik, mardlik, botirlik, dovyuraklik. Jasorat ko'rsatmoq. O'qizning barcha harakatlarini diqqat bilan kuzatgan Lola uning jasorati va mardligiga, chidam va sadoqatiga qoyil bo'ldi. Sh. Rashidov, Bo'rondan kuchli. O'ktam yangi yosh kolxozni oyoqqa qo'ymoqqa azm va jasorat bilan kirishdi. Oybek, O.v. shabadalar. Jo'ra-xonning qahramonligi, jasorati, yorqin xo-tirasi, ishlari qalblarda, hayotda abadiy qoladi. Nazarmat, Jo'rlar baland sayraydi. [Annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language, five volumes, volume 3 2007: 688]

In the "Etymological dictionary of the Uzbek language" Sh. Rahmatullayev gives the etymology of the lexeme courage as follows:

COURAGE: This Arabic word has the form *çasârat* (un) (ARS, 130); adopted into Uzbek by replacing the long vowel *â* with the vowel *â*; *çasârat* → *jasârat* (courage) is an infinitive of the first chapter (UAY, 568), "dovyuraklik", "mardlik" (ARS, 130) from the multi-meaning verb *çasara*, meaning "became brave" means bravery. (OTIL,

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I 274). In the Uzbek language, the adjectives courageous and uncourageous are made from this word. [Etymological dictionary of the Uzbek language 2003: 560]

BRAVE: This Arabic word has the form 'ajamat(un) (ARS, 524); It was accepted into the Uzbek language by replacing the vowel a with the consonant izgi with the consonant z: 'ažamat → azamat. This word is an infinitive of Chapter I (ATG, 143) derived from the verb 'azuma (ARS, 523), which means "became great", in Uzbek it means "big, huge, powerful, zabardast means the meanings of symbols like: great country, great young man; A man's name is also a horse (O'TIL, I, 30). [Annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language, five volumes, volume 1 2007: 30]

BRAVE: \a.,~, p — buyuklik, kattalik; faxr, g'urur] 1 Ko'rinish-tuzilishi e'tibori bilan juda katta; haybatli, ulkan. Magnificent maples. Azamat mountains. tsh When he looked back, [the father] had not seen such a grand construction at this age. R. Faizi. Spring has come to the desert.

2 Has great strength; powerful. People drive thirty or fifty grand cars. M. Jora. Those who absorb light from the sun.

3 Enthusiastic; is a price. hero The machine gunners repelled six more attacks of the enemy soldiers, who were closing in from all four sides and raining bullets. T. Rustamov. Mangu courage.

4 Physically mature; immediately There was no need to worry when her husband was standing next to her, like a lion, who would make a mountain roar. S. Ahmed, Ufq. In a place where every person is equal to gold, they imprison three innocent young men. You have turned four years old, you have become an azamat. "Murodkhan".

5 Indicates a relationship that records the ownership of such a sign-characteristic. Shakir put his hand on Ghairat's shoulder: Obba azamat, you are a wonderful young man! M. Hazratkulov, Jur'at. You are tired, azamat, go now, enter the bunker and sleep. I. Rahim, True love.

6 Azamat (male name). [Etymological dictionary of the Uzbek language 2003: 560]

To conclude, the historical-etymological characteristics of the noun units with the common name "Courage" have their own and acquired layers and are borrowed from

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Arabic, Persian, Mongolian, and Italian languages. The Arabic layer of possessive nouns is richer compared to other layers, which is characterized by the fact that the Arabic layer has a large role in the formation of the Uzbek language. When familiarizing with the explanations given in the etymological dictionary of the Uzbek language and the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the lexemes of bravery and azamat are the basic etymological meanings of these lexemes for today's symbols.

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